

Instrument validation format by expert judgment.

PhD in Education
University of Caldas

LETTER ADDRESSED TO THE JURY/VALIDATING EXPERT

Dear Teacher.

Receive a cordial greeting.

I would like to address this letter to request your kind collaboration in validating the data collection instruments designed for my doctoral thesis, entitled "Evolution of Mental Models of Environmental Awareness through Simulation of Environmental Events," aimed at fifth-semester Environmental Engineering students at the Central Unit of the Valle del Cauca University.

Your valuable experience and knowledge in the field are essential for assessing the relevance and rigor of these instruments. I would deeply appreciate any comments, suggestions, or adjustments you deem appropriate to strengthen their validity and scientific suitability.

I express my sincere gratitude for your time, willingness, and contribution to this process. I look forward to your comments and feedback.

Sincerely,

Harlys Rivas Perea

PhD Candidate in Education

University of Caldas

VALIDATION OF THE INSTRUMENT

1. IDENTIFICATION OF THE EXPERT

Full Name: _____

Identification Document: _____

Academic Background: _____

Institution/Affiliation: _____

2. IDENTIFICATION OF THE RESEARCH

Research Title:

Evolution of the mental model of environmental awareness through the application of teaching sequences focused on the simulation of environmental events.

General Objective: To understand the evolution of the mental model of environmental awareness through the application of didactic sequences focused on the simulation of environmental events.

Structure of the Instrument: The instrument consists of 21 questions, organized into four parts, the first collects information corresponding to the Epistemological dimension, the second part corresponds to the ontological dimension, the third corresponds to the cognitive-linguistic dimension and the fifth part to the motivational dimension.

3. INSTRUMENT ASSESSMENT INSTRUCTIONS

According to the following indicators, rate each item as appropriate.

Table 1. Instrument Assessment Instructions

CATEGORY	RATING	INDICATOR
SUFFICIENCY <hr/> Items belonging to the same dimension are sufficient to obtain its measurement.	1. Strongly disagree	The item does not meet the criterion for measuring the dimension.
	2. Disagree	The item measures some aspect of the dimension, but does not explore the dimension in depth in its context.
	3. Somewhat disagree	The item presents significant, but not entirely critical, problems.
	4. Neutral	The item does not show a clear trend; it neither fully meets nor fully fails to meet.
	5. Somewhat agree	The item partially meets the indicator, but requires minor adjustments.
	6. Agree	The item is adequate and aligns with the indicator assessed.
	7. Strongly agree	The item performs excellently; it is exemplary and fully relevant.
CLARITY <hr/> The item is easily understood, that is, its syntax and semantics are adequate.	1. Strongly disagree	The item is confusing and incomprehensible.
	2. Disagree	The item has significant deficiencies in meeting the criterion.
	3. Somewhat disagree	The item presents significant, but not entirely critical, problems.
	4. Neutral	The item does not show a clear trend; it neither fully meets nor fully fails to meet.
	5. Somewhat agree	The item partially meets the indicator, but requires minor adjustments.
	6. Agree	The item is adequate and aligns with the indicator assessed.
	7. Strongly agree	The item is entirely clear and precise.
COHERENCE <hr/> The item has a logical relationship with the dimension or indicator it is measuring.	1. Strongly disagree	The item is unrelated to the dimension it measures.
	2. Disagree	The item has significant deficiencies in meeting the criterion.
	3. Somewhat disagree	The item presents significant, but not entirely critical, problems.
	4. Neutral	The item does not show a clear trend; it neither fully meets nor fully fails to meet.
	5. Somewhat agree	The item partially meets the indicator, but requires minor adjustments.
	6. Agree	The item is adequate and clearly aligns with the indicator being assessed.
	7. Strongly agree	The item is fully consistent with the dimension
RELEVANCE <hr/>	1. Strongly disagree	The item is not relevant and does not add value.
	2. Disagree	The item has significant deficiencies in meeting the criterion.

The item is essential or important, that is, it must be included.	3. Somewhat disagree	The item presents significant, but not entirely critical, problems.
	4. Neutral	The item does not show a clear trend; it neither fully meets nor fully fails to meet.
	5. Somewhat agree	The item partially meets the indicator, but requires minor adjustments.
	6. Agree	The item is adequate and clearly aligns with the indicator assessed.
	7. Strongly agree	The item fully meets the criterion to achieve the research objectives.

Source: Adapted from Escobar-Pérez & Cuervo-Martínez (2008)

4. VALORACIÓN GENERAL DEL EVALUADOR DEL INSTRUMENTO

Dimension	Item	Sufficiency	Coherence	Relevance	Clarity	Observation
Epistemological	1					
	2					
	3					
	4					
	5					
	6					
	7					
Ontological	8					
	9					
	10					
	11					
	12					
Cognitive-Linguistic	13					
	14					
	15					
	16					
Motivational	17					
	18					
	19					
	20					
	21					

1. Does the instrument contain clear instructions for answering the sections? Yes _____ No _____

2. Does the instrument used allow for an adequate description of what is intended to be investigated? Yes _____ No _____

3. Likewise, if you consider that a question should be eliminated, please indicate which one(s) they would be:

4. Do you consider the instrument applicable? Yes _____ No

Signature of expert/evaluator:

Date: _____